

Analysis and asset Supply Chain Water Flow Dynamics Model System - NETLOGO with Autoregressive Inte- grated Moving Average (ARIMA)

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Abstract. The work presented in this article constitutes a contribution to the modeling and prediction of demand in water flow, using a NETLOGO Dynamic System Model. This work shows how historical water flow data can be used to contrast the results obtained in the created simulation model.

Historical flow data was used to develop autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) models, using Box-Jenkins, to evaluate the model's effectiveness in forecasting water flow.

Keywords: Supply Chain, Climate Change, Sustainable Development Goals 2030, Water Management, Simulation, Reservoir Logistics Model, Water Scarcity. First Section, Netlogo, Dynamic Model System.

1 Introduction

Climate change, as a consequence of global warming, is a phenomenon that directly and mainly affects the vital resources on our planet. This generates a critical condition in the medium term for our subsistence and leads to the need to implement environmental regulation policies. Although the regulatory framework and the actions in favor exist, the reality shows great waste, without corresponding reuse. These practices, restrictions and policies have been implemented in several developing countries, however, pollution, global warming and the conservation of natural resources is not fully viable without a regulatory framework in place. In this context, we must consider and emphasize that a vital element such as water only gives us the possibility of managing it.

The situation raised has accentuated a notable interest in the study and development of environmental impact and care of natural resources. Nevertheless, the reality presents great abuses and waste of scarce resources, where each of the participants acts passively or non-existent, without solving the root problems. An example of this is water. The situation is not only a consequence of climate change, but also depends on other drivers of global change, such as population growth, land-use changes, urbanization and concentration in urban areas. For example, while population growth in the 20th century tripled, from 1.8 billion to 6 billion people, water withdrawal during the same period increased sixfold. That is clearly unsustainable without controlled use. If all the water on Earth is considered, 97.5% is found in the seas and oceans and that available in rivers, lakes and reservoirs. Immediate human consumption represents no more than a mere 0.007% of the total equivalent of approximately 42 000 km³. In the last 30 years, the panorama is disturbing. While in 1975 the availability was around 13000 m³ per person, it has now been reduced to 6000 m³; Meanwhile, water quality has also deteriorated severely¹.

The water crisis, characterized by historically low flows and no prospect of improvement in the coming years, is aggravated by inefficient and inequitable distribution and suboptimal water productivity at the farm level. This situation makes the management and maintenance of water a priority.

Focusing on this problematic situation, a **Dynamic System Model in Netlogo** (FIGURE 1) has been developed to project future water reserves and consumption in the location of Mendoza-Argentina.

¹ (Beek, Water Resource Systems Planning and Management, 2017)

Figure 1: Dynamic System Model in Netlogo

2 Literature Review: Demand Forecasting

Demand forecasting is a crucial component in modern organizations that are subject to abrupt and significant changes, affecting even the most established structures. Forecasts are the sign of survival and the language of business in the world. A forecast is a science of estimating the future level of some variables, most often demand, but also others, such as supply or price.

This concept leads us to consider and categorize four types of forecasts:

- Time series
- Qualitative
- Causal
- Simulation

A time series is nothing more than observations according to the chronological order of time. Time series forecasting models use mathematical techniques based on historical data to forecast demand. It is based on the hypothesis that the future is an expansion of the past, which is why we can use historical data to forecast.

Many studies have been conducted on demand forecasting in various domains through time series analysis. These studies demonstrate the importance and applicability of forecasting in a variety of industries.

The reliability of the forecast depends on the characteristics of the time series. Therefore, accuracy will be aligned with greater stability and periodicity of the series.

To model time series, we can work with traditional statistical models that include moving average, exponential smoothing, and ARIMA (autoregressive integrated moving average). These models are linear because future values tend to be linear functions of past data.

2.1 Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average

An ARIMA model is labeled as ARIMA (p, d, q), where:

- **p** is the number of autoregressive terms

The autoregressive process assumes that the observation (Y_t) is a linear function of its previous values, which is mathematically expressed by the equation:

$$Y_t = \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Each observation (Y_t) consists of a random component (random shock, (ε)) and a linear combination of previous observations. The coefficient (α_1) in this equation is the autoregression coefficient.

- **d** is the number of differences

The behavior of time series can be affected by the cumulative effect of some processes. For example, the stock levels of goods are constantly modified by consumption and supply, but the average level essentially depends on the cumulative effect of instantaneous changes during the period between inventories. Although short-term stock values may fluctuate significantly around this average value, the long-term level of the series will remain unchanged. A time series determined by the cumulative effect of an activity belongs to the class of integrated processes. Even if the behavior of a series is erratic, the differences from one observation to the next can be relatively low or even oscillate around a constant value for a process observed at different time intervals. This stationarity of the difference series for an integrated process is a crucial characteristic from the statistical analysis perspective of time series. Integrated processes are the archetype of non-stationary series. A first-order differentiation assumes that the difference between two

successive values of (Y) is constant. An integrated process is defined by equation (2) where the random disturbance (ε_t) is a white noise.

$$Y_t = Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

- q is the number of moving averages

The current value of a moving average process is a linear combination of the current disturbance with one or more previous disturbances. The order of the moving average indicates the number of previous periods incorporated into the current value. Therefore, a moving average is defined by equation (3).

$$Y_t = \varepsilon_t - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} \quad (3)$$

Results and Discussion

In this article, the projection of the Mendoza River flows based on real data is carried out, and the precision and characteristics are studied. This study compares the effectiveness of flow projections of the Mendoza River considering two methodologies:

- ARIMA
- DMS NETLOGO.

The study covers three parts to consider: identification, estimation, and verification. The model shown in Figure 2 represents the flows of the Mendoza River from 1956 to 2023.

Figure 2: Mendoza River's Flow from 1956 to 2023.

In an autoregressive model, the endogenous variable of a period (t) is explained by its own observations from previous periods, with an added error term. In the case of stationary processes with a normal distribution, the statistical theory of stochastic processes states that, under certain prior conditions, every (Y_t) can be expressed as a linear combination of its past values (systematic part) plus an error term (innovation).

In an ARIMA model, its preponderance lies in being defined as “ergodic,” which allows inferring values of a series based on the information provided by its own past, achieving consistent estimators.

In our case, we analyze the functions:

- **AUTOCORRELATION (ACF):** The relationship that exists in the memory of the observed series over time (Figure 3).
- **PARTIAL AUTOCORRELATION (PACF):** The partial autocorrelation function is a measure of the correlation between observations of a time series that are separated by (k) time units ((Y_t) and (Y_{t-k})), after adjusting for the presence of shorter lag terms ($(Y_{t-1}, Y_{t-2}, \dots, Y_{t-k-1})$) (Figure 4).

It is observed that there is no explosiveness, confirming decreasing dependence over time. That is, the last observation receives a smaller weight, and the expectation has a more significant weight. This reflects the fact that in a stationary process, the further into the future we predict, the greater the uncertainty.

Figure 3: Autocorrelation function.

Figure 4: Partial autocorrelation function

In the study, an ARIMA forecast is developed with lags of 6, 12, and 24 observations, calculating the standard deviation of the error relative to the actual values in the period 2019-2023 and the one obtained with NETLOGO (Table 1):

	24 months	12 months	6 months	NETLOGO
Deves. Stand	19	19	25	16

Table 1: Devest Std. Errors.

The figures(Figure 5) below illustrate the accuracy of various forecasting methods compared to actual results. According to the standard deviation, the NetLogo method demonstrates greater accuracy than the ARIMA method.

Figure 5: Comparison between MENDOZA RIVER'S flow against ARIMA and NETLOGO

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